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Utilization of New Technologies For Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The study adopted a descriptive research design. Two objectives, research questions and hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 30 respondents. The entire population was adopted due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire titled "Questionnaire On Utilization Of New Technologies For Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers (QUNTIPGCL)". The instrument was validated by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation and two specialists in guidance and counselling. Cronbach alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained. A total number of 30 copies of the questionnaire were administered while a total of 30 were retrieved. Therefore, the analyses were made based on the total number of questionnaire retrieved. The Mean and standard deviation were adopted to analyze the research questions while the t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses. Findings revealed that respondents utilize interactive white board and social media technology, to a moderate extent while they utilize interactive whiteboard to a small extent for instructional purposes. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended among others that, university administrators should organize regular training and retraining programmes for lecturers to enable them update their ICT skills so as to utilize new technologies for instructional purpose.

Keywords: information and communication technology, guidance, counselling, lecturers

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning involves purposeful and meaningful transfer of knowledge, skills, competences and attitude formation to human beings either in the formal or informal setup. The new era of information and communication technology (ICT) known as information age has changed the traditional ways of learning in the classroom to more interesting and fascinating one characterized with active interactive and evaluative learning. The technology revolution has not only change the way the society learns but also the way the world communicates, conducts businesses and even carry out day-to-day activities. Hamony (2020) defined Technology as the systematic application of scientific or other organized knowledge to practical tasks. Guidance and counselling lecturers use new technologies to enhance teaching and learning through active participation of the students. Guidance and counselling

lecturers do this by allowing students to source for information online and discuss it with them in the classroom. The teachers also post basic information such as course outlines or important topics on social network like group chat room where students can access such information.

The Guidance and counselling lecturers' role in the new technologies is to use these technologies in the course of teaching so that student would be used to it since students are bound to use these new technologies in their place of work on graduation. As the world has become a global village through the worldwide web (www) business education as a profession that prepares an individual for a career in business and also to be an intelligent consumer of economic goods and services need to be properly positioned in this global village through the use of these new technologies for instructional purpose.

New technologies are the modern tools (electronic tools) that are used to enhance teaching and learning. The new technologies are also used in the offices where students are to be employed at the end of their programme. The exposure to these technologies in the course of students' training will help them to be familiar and acquainted with the technologies in the classroom and alternatively at their places of work upon graduation. Students that are exposed to new technologies in guidance and counselling programme can compete favourably with their counterparts all over the world. When these tools are not properly utilized for instructions in guidance and counselling programme, the students could lack the requisite knowledge required to fit into today's digital world.

New technologies are made up of information and communication technologies (ICT) and are represented by several tools like computers, internet and intranet, global system of communication (GSM), worldwide web (www), teleconferencing and video-conferencing devices and mobile technologies. Others are smart/interactive white board, dedicated e-learning centres, search engines and machines such as google, e-library and projectors. Multimedia that combine sound, images, graphics, video and text in a single presentation are also part of it (Ebisine, 2019). According to Amiaya (2018), there are also new technologies for data capturing, multimedia software for simulations, publishing and presentation, digital recording, computer and computer projection technology that enhances teaching and learning.

New technologies have been found to possess the capacity to improve instructions in the Guidance and counseling classroom (Lefebure, Deaudelin & Loiselle, 2019). New technologies have the great potential to support education across curriculum, thus, providing opportunities for an effective communication between teachers and students in ways that have not been possible before. Many researchers and theories have asserted that the use of new technological tools such as computers and others can help students to become more knowledgeable, reduce the amount of direct instruction given to students and give the teachers the opportunity to provide personalized instruction for students with special needs (Shamatha, Peressini & Meymaris, 2020). Grabe and Grabe (2020) posited that new technology gadgets such as social media, visuals, audio-visual and E-learning are central to developing student's skills and competencies, motivation and knowledge.

Social media are avenues in which people interact and also socialize via special platforms established for such purposes in the internet. Through these platforms people can create, share or exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. Social media is a group of internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0 and allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2020). Social media comprises of activities that involve socializing and networking online through words, pictures, and videos. It is redefining how we relate to each other as humans and how we as humans relate to the organizations that serve us or the ones we serve. It is about dialogue that is, a two-way discussions bringing people together to discover and share information (Solis, 2018). Laurenti (2019) posited that social media when used in guidance and counselling programme enhances collaboration, which allows students to work together on projects beyond their individual capability. Students' problem-solving skills are often better developed and enhanced in a collaborative environment which social media amply offers.

Statement of the Problem

The popularity and increased access to ICT accelerated the call for the adoption of new technologies in every aspect of education. These have increased the expectations of business education students to see

these technologies used in the process of teaching and learning. It is therefore sad to note that traditional chalk board method is still in use as a medium of instruction a tertiary institution.

The traditional methods of instruction which focuses on the teacher as the only source of information has changed due to the introduction of new technologies. These new technology when use for instruction enhances student participation, problem solving collaborative environment, networking and above all, students' better understanding of the subject matter.

The inability of Guidance and counselling students to fit into digital ways of carrying out activities could be traced to the mode of instructions that was used in the process of their training in universities. It is against this background that this study sought to determine the Utilization Of New Technologies For Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine Utilization Of New Technologies For Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to determine the extent:

1. Interactive white board is utilized for instructional Purpose by Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities.
2. Social media is utilized for Instructional Purpose by Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent is interactive whiteboard utilized for Instructional Purpose by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent are social media utilized for Instructional Purpose by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent they utilize interactive whiteboard for Instructional Purpose in Rivers State Universities.
2. Male and female Guidance and Counselling Lecturers do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent they utilize social media technology for Instructional Purpose In Rivers State Universities.

METHODS

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted of 30 respondents. The entire population was adopted due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire titled'' Questionnaire On Utilization Of New Technologies For Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers (QUNTIPGCL). The instrument was validated by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation and two specialists in guidance and counselling. Chrombach alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument. A total number of 30 copies of the questionnaire were administered while a total of 30 were retrieved. Therefore, the analyses were made based on the total number of questionnaire retrieved. The Mean and standard deviation were adopted to analyze the research questions while the t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent is interactive whiteboard utilized for Instructional Purpose By Guidance And Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities ?*

Table 1. Respondents’ mean ratings and standard deviation on the extent interactive whiteboard are utilized for instructional purpose N = 30

S/N	Items on utilization of interactive whiteboard	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
I utilize interactive whiteboard:				
1.	To display information about subject matter so as to motivate students	1.51	1.08	Small Extent
2.	To project major contents that will enhance students understanding	1.91	1.19	Small Extent
3.	To recall previous lessons so as to help students with special needs	1.57	0.96	Small Extent
4.	To project information that will engage students learning that day.	1.37	0.82	Very Small extent
5.	To project information that will enhance classroom activities.	1.43	1.24	Very Small extent
6.	To highlight points that will remove learning difficulties.	1.10	0.99	Very Small extent
7.	To repeat previous information that can help students to overcome literacy problems	1.48	0.92	Very Small extent
8.	To display images from the computer that will help to reduce distraction among students with special needs.	1.39	0.84	Very Small extent
9.	To project concepts that will help to keep students on tasks for a productive period of time.	1.63	0.96	Small Extent
10.	To display concepts in the topic being taught for sequential explanation.	1.49	0.79	Very Small extent
11.	To display sharp and captivating information that will increase students’ interest in the teaching and learning process.	1.99	1.18	Small Extent
Cluster Mean		1.53		Small Extent

Data in Table 1 shows that out of the 11 items listed on utilization of interactive white board, respondents indicated that they utilize five items to a small extent while the remaining six items are utilized at a very small extent. The cluster mean score of 1.53 shows that on the whole, respondents utilized interactive whiteboard for instructional purposes to a small extent. The standard deviations for all the items are within the same range showing that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Research Question 2: *To what extent are social media utilized for Instructional Purpose by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers In Rivers State Universities?*

Data relating to this research question are analyzed and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Respondents’ mean ratings and standard deviation on the extent social media are utilized for instructional delivery N = 30

S/N	Items on utilization of social media	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
I utilize Facebook:				
12.	To schedule classroom events for students.	2.79	1.2	Moderate extent
13.	To post notes about a topic for students to read.	3.20	1.17	Moderate extent
14.	To provide a reminder to students about upcoming classroom events or activities.	3.69	0.08	Great Extent
15.	To teach students how to include citations with an application called CitMe	3.30	1.65	Moderate extent
16.	To know the books that students are reading through an	2.35	1.16	Moderate extent

- application called **WeRead**.
17. To create classroom groups for effective communication between lecturers and students. 3.78 1.18 Great Extent
 18. To make announcements and share interesting Websites that will help to educate students 2.55 1.09 Moderate extent
- I utilize YouTube:**
19. To search for on-topic videos that can be used in the classroom to bring lessons to life or become memorable. 1.43 0.71 Very Small Extent
 20. To upload videos of class sessions so that students can view them anywhere. 1.69 0.73 Small Extent
- I utilize TWITTER**
21. To create a feedback platform or group for classroom members. 3.25 0.69 Moderate extent
 22. To tweet about upcoming assignments, events and class news. 1.39 0.76 Very Small Extent
 23. To help students keep up with latest teaching trend by “tweeting” them. 3.30 0.82 Moderate extent
 24. To post supplementary like links to articles and videos so that students can continue to learn even when class is over. 2.33 1.00 Small Extent

Cluster Mean	2.69	Moderate Extent
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Data on Table 2 shows that four of the items are being utilized for instructional purpose at a great extent. Out of the 13 social media technology listed, respondents utilize seven at a moderate extent, two at small extent and the rest at a very small extent. The cluster means score of 2.69 show that on the whole, respondents in the area of the study utilize social media technology for instructional delivery at a moderate extent. The standard deviations for all the items are within the same range showing that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Male and female Guidance and Counselling Lecturers do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent they utilize interactive whiteboard for instructional delivery in universities in Rivers State.

This null hypothesis was tested using t-test and the results are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Summary of t-test analysis of male and female respondents on the extent they utilize interactive white board for instructional purpose

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	α	df	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Male	5	1.75	0.96	0.05	28	0.49	1.96	Not significant
Female	25	1.53	0.81					

Table 3 show that the calculated t - value of 0.49 is less than the critical t -value of 1.96 ($1.18 < 1.96$) at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom. This means that the respondents did not differ significantly in their mean ratings and extent they utilize interactive white board for instructional delivery. Therefore, the null hypothesis was upheld.

Hypothesis 2: Male and female Guidance and Counselling Lecturers do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent they utilize social media technology for Instructional Purpose In Rivers State Universities.

This null hypothesis was tested using t-test and the results are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Summary of t-test analysis of male and female respondents on the extent they utilize social media for instructional purpose

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	α	df	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Male	5	3.16	0.76	0.05	28	0.42	1.96	Not significant
Female	25	2.96	1.64					

Table 6 show that the calculated t - value of 0.42 is less than the critical t -value of 1.96 ($0.75 < 1.96$) at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom. This means that the respondents did not differ significantly in their mean ratings and extent they utilize social media for instructional purposes. Therefore, the null hypothesis was upheld.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Findings of the study were discussed as follows:

Utilization of interactive white board for instructional purposes

Findings of the study revealed that respondents in the area of the study utilize interactive white board for instructional delivery at small extent. The finding of the study concurred with that of Ajelabi (2025) which found that the extent of utilization of interactive white board by lecturers is low. This supports the earlier findings of Ozgen and Ismail (2019) which disclosed that lecturers continue to use traditional teaching strategies more often because they lack adequate training in the utilization of more complex new technologies.

The data collected showed that respondents utilize interactive white board at a very small extent while others utilize them at small extent for instructional purposes. This could be as a result of several constraints to utilization of new technologies which according to Tufan (2018) ranges from technical problems to insufficiency of e-materials. It is therefore clear that the utilization of interactive white board in business education programme in Nigeria is still in its developmental stage. Turel and Johnson (2020) stated that lecturers’ inadequate utilization of interactive white board in teaching hinder effective instructional delivery and the ability to give business education students with opportunities to work as individuals, in pairs, as well as in small and large groups in order to achieve their learning goals.

According to Nwaukwa (2019) in this computer era, everything is being computerized from business to office work and education. This demands that students should be taught with new technologies so as to withstand the challenges of the present dynamic world. It is also obvious that what determines the extent of utilization of new technologies in classroom instruction is availability. This is to say that where the new technologies are available, by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers will be motivated to acquire the skills for their utilization in instructional delivery (Nwaukwa, 2019). From the evidence of the study that business educators utilize interactive white board for instructional purposes at a small extent, it implies that recommendations by researchers and educators for the full utilization of these new technologies to support teaching and learning are not receiving adequate consideration. The negative effect of this situation is that, on graduation, business education students will be unable to meet the technological demands of business enterprises and the society at large.

Utilization of social media technology for instructional purpose

Findings of the study revealed that by Guidance and Counselling Lecturers in the area of the study utilize social media for instructional purposes at moderate extent. The findings of the study is in agreement with that of Mamman and Nwabufu (2018) which revealed that lecturers in tertiary institutions utilize to a moderate extent facebook, youtube and twitter among others for instructional purposes. Mamman and Nwabufu (2018) stated that lecturers use social media more for personal purposes to a very great extent than for professional purposes. Abdullahi, Joshua and Hannah (2024) disclosed that while lecturers utilize Facebook to a great extent, they however, utilize other social media such as Whatsapp, Youtube, and

Google+ among others at moderate extent. Abdullahi Joshua and Hannah stated that the inability of lecturers to adequately utilize social media technologies for instructional purposes could be as a result of poor internet connectivity, epileptic power supply and lecturers' lack of interest in utilizing ICT in teaching.

The findings of the study revealed that most of the social media listed are being utilized to a very and great extent respectively by respondents for instructional delivery while others to a moderate extent. This is in line with the findings of Okoli and Idele (2018) which reported that respondents utilize social media technologies such as Facebook and Whatsapp at great extent while others such as twitter and blogs were utilized to a moderate extent.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of this study, one can see that lots of new technologies which could help in improving the professional practices of business educators are utilized at small and moderate extent. Despite the increasing importance of these new technologies in the achievement of respondents' goals, they have not been utilized to a great extent in tertiary institutions. Utilization of new technologies to a great extent will not only revolutionize instructional delivery, they will also stimulate the development of students' innate scientific and critical thinking abilities. Hence, the researcher concluded that there is need for training of business educators on how to effectively utilize these new technologies to ensure effective instructional delivery in the field of Guidance and Counselling at all tertiary levels.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University administrators should organize regular training and retraining programmes for lecturers to enable them update their ICT skills so as to utilize new technologies for instructional purposes.
2. The federal and state governments should ensure adequate provision of new technologies for use by lecturers in the fields of Business Education because new technologies are expensive to acquire and cannot be left in the hands of universities alone.

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